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A Brief Report of Archaeological Explorations in the Ganaur, Tehsil, District, Sonipat, Haryana

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Abstract

This paper is a preliminary report of village-to-village survey of Ganaur Tehsil, Sonipat district, Haryana. During the month of March 2018, a total number of 42 archaeological sites were documented and 26 sites are new findings. This venture aims to find general information about the archaeological sites in the region for my Ph.D. Research Work. The result of this survey will address a number of problems such of size of the settlements, geo-coordinates etc.

Key-Words : Explorations, Archaeological Remains.

Introduction

The study area lies in the south-eastern part of Haryana and one of the Tehsil of Sonipat District. This area comes under Yamuna River Plain. The area is rich in archaeological remains and the fact it has been proved by the explorations conducted by various scholars. The credit for initiating archaeological field work goes to some researcher like Dr. Sliak Ram, Dr. Dutt and Dr. R.C. Thakran.

Dr. Sliak Ram Carried out explorations for their Ph. D. work in Rohtak and Hisar District of Haryana and reported some sites. Some sculptures and many more (Ram Sliak: 1972). After some time, Dr. Dutt also explored the area in 1980 for the work on topic PGW in Haryana in the area and brought to light some site from this area during his research (Dutt: 1980). Later Dr. R. C. Thakran Carried out explorations in South-Eastern Haryana and reported some new Archaeological sites. Some sculptures and many more (Thakran, R. C.: 2000). With this archaeological background present researcher commence the village-to-village survey in Sonipat district, Haryana.

Drainage system

The area under present study is a part of Yamuna river plain and it has poor surface drainage. Due to poor surface drainage and system of abundant paleo-channels, water table is very high. The general slope of the district is from north to south. The Yamuna river makes a common boundary of about 49 kilometers between the Sonipat district and Uttar Pradesh State and present study area is a part of Sonipat District (Thakran, R. C.: 2000). During this course, the river falls in elevation from 218 meters to 209 meters giving it a very gentle gradient and forms a flood plain on eastern side of its bed. Seepage from the Yamuna river, distributaries and field channels taking off from Bhalaut Branch are the conditions mainly responsible for high sub-surface water level in the district. In most of the area water-logged and partially waterlogged conditions are a rule. So, irrigation in the district is mostly done by canals and tube wells (Sonipat Gazetteer, 1990: 09).

Methodology

- 1) The present researcher conducted an extensive village-to-village survey in the region.
- 2) A GPS handset was used to record correct co-ordinates of the sites.
- 3) Proper sampling of the pottery and other remains from the surface and exposed sections was done.
- 4) On the basis of ecological conditions and detailed analysis of the ancient settlements, different categories of the sites like regional centers, villages, industrial centers and camp sites have been identified. The main emphasis was laid on locating sites and on observing the distribution pattern of the cultural remains in the area. The date of the sites was decided on the basis of occurrence of diagnostic ceramic shapes of ancient cultures. The estimation about the size of the sites was made on the basis of the area, up to which cultural deposit was found.
- 5) Cultural material discovered from the survey and housed in different museums was analyzed and studied to address the problems.
- 6) The available published literature and survey reports including unpublished dissertations were examined and their data was also included in this study. Following table 1 is the list of sites explored by researchers:

Table 1 Showing explored sites along with geo-references, previous work and cultural sequence.

Sr.No.	Site Name	Latitude	Longitude	Area (Ek)	Previous Work	Culture Sequence
1.	Agwanpur	29°06'24.0"	76°59'36.0"	6	Sliak Ram, R.C.Thakran	GW, His (RW), Med.
2.	Ahulana	29°11'44.0"	76°57'38.5"	10	Sliak Ram, R.C.Thakran	LH, PGW.
3.	Atail	29°11'13.0"	76°57'26.0"	2	New	His, Med.
4.	Bajana Khurd	29°09'17.0"	76°52'11.0"	2	R.C.Thakran	His(RW), E.Med.
5.	Balanpur	29°10'01.0"	76°57'38.0"	2	Dutt, Ram, Sliak R.C.Thakran	PGW, His (Kusana), E.Med.
6.	Bali Qutbapur	29°11'42.0"	76°54'41.0"	10	Sliak Ram, R.C.Thakran	His.
7.	Bhadana	29°02'54.3"	77°02'20.5"	3	R.C.Thakran	RW, E.Med.
8.	Bhagan	29°04'07.8"	77°02'46.2"	2	R.C.Thakran	RW, E.Med.
9.	Bhamar	29°08'51.0"	76°56'42.0"	8	Sliak Ram, R.C.Thakran	His (RW), E.Med.
10.	Bhrate	29°05'10.0"	77°00'42.0"	4	New	His, Med.
11.	Bhora rasulpur-1	29°11'06.0"	76°59'14.0"	2	New	His, Med.
12.	Bhora rasulpur-2	29°10'57.0"	76°58'44.0"	2	New	His, Med.
13.	Chindoli	29°07'45.0"	77°07'02.0"	6	New	His.
14.	Chirsami	29°09'34.0"	77°02'37.0"	3	Sliak Ram, R.C.Thakran	GW, His (RW), E.Med.
15.	Dabarpur	29°07'30.0"	76°53'16.0"	2	New	Med.
16.	Datauli	29°09'39.0"	77°05'01.0"	2	R.C.Thakran	LH, PGW (GW), His(RW), Kusana), E.Med.
17.	Gannaur	29°07'20.0"	77°01'11.0"	4	R.C.Thakran	His (RW), Med.
18.	Gujjar Kheri	29°09'36.0"	76°58'21.0"	20	R.C.Thakran	His (RW).
19.	Gummar	29°07'50.0"	76°59'33.0"	2	Sliak Ram, R.C.Thakran	PGW (BSW), His (RW, NBPW).
20.	Jaffarpur-1	29°10'28.0"	76°59'52.0"	2	New	His.
21.	Jaffarpur-2	29°10'09.0"	76°59'42.0"	4	New	His.

22.	Jalalabad	29°09'01.0"	76°59'32.0"	12	New	Med.
23.	Kheni Tega-1	29°07'56.0"	77°04'32.0"	2	New	His.
24.	Kheni Tega-2	29°08'03.7"	77°05'11.6"	3	R.C.Thakran	RW, E.Med.
25.	Khubru	29°09'29.0"	76°56'25.0"	2	New	His, Med.
26.	Machrii	29°07'58.0"	76°58'50.0"	5	New	His.
27.	Mahmudpur	29°07'55.0"	76°54'17.0"	10	New	LMH, LH, His.
28.	Panchi Jattan	29°05'20.0"	76°58'44.0"	4	New	His.
29.	Panchi Gujran	29°09'31.0"	77°00'57.0"	5	Silak Ram, R.C.Thakran	GW, His (RW), Med.
30.	Pipili Khera	28°06'04.0"	77°03'37.0"	10	Silak Ram, R.C.Thakran	GW, BSW, His.
31.	Pugthia-1	29°10'59.0"	76°52'12.0"	4	New	His. Med.
32.	Pugthia-2	29°11'49.0"	76°51'52.0"	4	New	His. Med.
33.	Purkhas Rathi	29°08'55.0"	76°56'40.0"	4	New	His. Med.
34.	Rajlu Garhi	29°05'25.0"	77°00'52.0"	10	New	LH, His.
35.	Ram Nagar	29°05'38.0"	77°05'21.0"	2	New	His. Med.
36.	Rasulpur	29°05'49.0"	77°07'36.0"	3	New	His. Med.
37.	Saiya Khera	29°08'12.0"	76°55'33.0"	4	New	His.
38.	Sanpera	29°06'14.0"	77°04'24.0"	5	New	His.
39.	Shatwaili	29°06'04.2"	76°55'03.6"	2	New	Med.
40.	Sirchana	29°10'38.0"	76°54'07.0"	2	New	His. Med.
41.	Tewni	29°09'32.0"	76°53'36.0"	6	Silak Ram	His. Med.
42.	Udespur	29°06'01.0"	76°59'14.0"	2	New	Med.

MH=Mature Harappan, LH=Late Harappan, PGW=Painted Grey Ware, Hist=Historical, Med=Medieval.

Table 2 showing number of sites of different periods

S.no	Period	No of Sites
1	Mature Harappan	02
2	Late Harappan	04
3	PGW	07
4	Historical	37
5	Medieval	26

Discussion

The antiquity of the study area can be traced back to proto-historic times. Archaeological explorations have revealed that the earliest settlers in the regions belong to Harappan culture. So far as not even a single site belongs to Pre-Harappan period (Ghaggar-Hakra/Hakra culture) and Early Harappan Period has been reported in the area. But in the adjoining area a number of sites of late fourth millennium BCE has been reported (Rao et al/2005: 60-68; Dangl 2007: 205-212).

Mature Harappan period

Archaeological explorations have revealed that the earliest settlers in the regions belong to Mature Harappan culture. Only two sites have yielded remains of Mature Harappan period.

Only a few classical Harappan shapes viz. perforated jar, dish-on-stand vases were recovered from the surface. Some sherds akin to Ganeswar-Jodhpura pottery were also found from the region. Quantity of classical Harappan shapes such as perforated jar, long stem dish-on-stand,

beakers, painted jars, nail headed bowls and basins are very less on the surface of the sites. I conducted extensive explorations in the entire Sonapat District and we can conclude that as we move south of the basin quantity of classical Harappan pottery reduces (Kumar, M. 2011: 168-178).

Late Harappan Period.

The second cultural phase in the proto-history of this region is distinguished by the Late Harappan culture or degenerate phase of urban Harappans. Four sites yielded the remains of this phase. The classical Harappan shapes like globlets, perforated jars and classical Harappan paintings fell out of use but some shapes such as beakers, nail headed bowls, dish-on-stands with long stems etc continue with modifications. The common pottery types are dish-on-stands with ribbed junctions, dish-on-stands with broad and short stands, vases with projected undercut rims, jars with wide and narrow mouths, globular vases with flanged rims, beakers without-turned rims and flasks treated with fine red slip. Out of total 04 Late Harappan sites, two were occupied for the first time, two sites of the Mature Harappan period were preferred by the late Harappan peoples in absence of excavation it is very difficult to say that weather there is a cultural break between the Harappans and Late Harappans (Kumar, M. 2011: 168-178).

Painted Grey Ware Period

During the proto historic period, the last phase is characterized by the advent of the PGW people. The exploration yielded 07 PGW sites. The excavation at Bhagwanpura and Madina (Kumar et al.2009: 114) threw light on the relationship between the late Harappan and PGW people

Historical and Medieval period

Forty sites of historical period were explored. The number of sites indicated that the after 600 BCE the area under present study was thickly populated as compare to proto-historic period. Common shapes of historical pottery were represented by bowls with incurved rim, carinated cooking handis, vases, spouted vases, basins, lid, incense burner. Pottery of later Kushana and Gupta period is less painted as compare to the pottery of Rangmahal. Naurangabad (Sanger 2005:191-195) and Kokhrakakot (Kumar, M. 1996) were the regional centers during the historical period. Both areas are located very near to the study area.

Twenty-two sites of medieval period were explored during the survey. Main shapes include sharp edged bowls, vases, pots etc. a few sherds of glazed ware were also collected during the explorations.

Conclusion

The researchers conducted extensive village-to-village survey in the region and recorded sites with the help of GPS, besides size of settlements and other vital information. This has helped us to correct the earlier recording of sites and their size. Recently some scholars surveyed various parts of Haryana addressing this problem (Dangi 2007; Singh et al/2010: 37-53 and 2011: 88-106). Future researchers shall have data on which they can easily bank upon.

During the survey it was noticed that most of the archaeological sites are either converted into the agriculture fields or the soil is removed for development purpose. The situation is very grim because in a few years it will be very difficult for the archaeologists to spot any site for excavation. Even today it is very hard to spot an intact mound. Hence the present study has its own importance as the sites are now recorded for posterity which may not exist in future.

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